

COcyber Cybersphere Insights

June 2026

As COcyber reaches its final month, this edition highlights new features now available on the [COcyber Platform](#), including Partner Research, the Projects Landscape, and the Repository of Practices.

These tools are designed to **help users find relevant cybersecurity partners**, explore the **European project ecosystem**, and **access knowledge** from the civilian and defence cybersecurity landscape

It also looks ahead to the **COcyber final conference** and brings together five **Cyber Duality podcast** episodes now available on YouTube.

COcyber Platform Features

Looking for your next cybersecurity partner?

Our COcyber **Partner Research feature** helps you discover relevant partners in Europe's civilian and defence **cybersecurity ecosystem** through a curated directory.

Built around the **JRC cybersecurity taxonomy** developed by the **European Commission's Joint Research Centre**, it allows users to search by knowledge domain, technology, sector and use case, then request moderated introductions through the platform.

From profile claim to moderated introduction, the feature is designed to support purposeful connections:

- ✓ Verified profiles
- ✓ Smarter matching
- ✓ Trusted connections

[Find your Partner](#)

Projects' Landscape

Want to explore the European cybersecurity project ecosystem?

The **COcyber Projects Landscape** provides an interactive overview of EU funded cybersecurity projects across Horizon Europe and Digital Europe.

The feature helps users better understand ongoing initiatives, identify thematic connections, and discover organisations active across different cybersecurity domains and technology areas.

[Access the projects' landscape](#)

Looking for practical ways to strengthen civil - defence cybersecurity cooperation?

Explore our [COcyber Platform Repository of Practices](#): 11 validated best practices and 7 strategic guidelines based on 600+ reviewed sources.

Designed for policy makers, practitioners, and researchers, the repository brings together transferable, evidence-based models to support stronger cyber cooperation in Europe.

Discover validated best practices

Browse strategic guidelines

Access the full methodology and report

Cyber cooperation made easier

Explore best practices

Funded by
the European Union

ECCC
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE

[Explore the best practices](#)

Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast

How do cybersecurity experts see the challenges, gaps, and future of cooperation between civilian and defence actors in Europe?

Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast continues to explore this question through short conversations with experts working across cybersecurity policy, research, innovation, skills, and operational cooperation.

With five episodes now available, the series brings together insights on:

- 1. Fast Attackers, Slow Defenders: The Real Cybersecurity Imbalance**
- 2. Strengthening Europe's Cybersecurity: Coordination, Innovation, and Sovereignty**
- 3. Cybersecurity Capacity Building: Language, Resilience and Trust Across Sectors**
- 4. Building Cyber Resilience in Europe: Skills, Trust, and Cooperation**
- 5. Why Europe's Cyber Future Depends on Human Skills**

The screenshot shows the Spotify interface for the 'Cyber Duality: A COcyber Podcast'. On the left is the main podcast card, which includes the title, the host 'COcyber EU', and a description: 'How do cybersecurity experts see the challenges, gaps, and future of cooperation between civilian and defence actors in Europe?'. Below the description are icons for 'Play latest', 'Bookmark', 'Share', and 'More options'. On the right is a list of the five episodes, each with a numbered thumbnail, the episode title, the host 'COcyber EU', and the release date. The episodes are:

1. Why Europe's Cyber Future Depends on Human Skills (18:49, 7 views, 1 day ago)
2. Building Cyber Resilience in Europe: Skills, Trust, and Cooperation (23:27, 42 views, 2 weeks ago)
3. Cybersecurity Capacity Building: Language, Resilience and Trust Across Sectors (14:56, 11 views, 2 weeks ago)
4. Strengthening Europe's Cybersecurity: Coordination, Innovation, and Sovereignty (11:44, 19 views, 2 weeks ago)
5. Fast Attackers, Slow Defenders: The Real Cybersecurity Imbalance (12:23, 6 views, 2 weeks ago)

[Listen to Cyber Duality](#)

COcyber Final Conference

A Unified Response to Multiple Threats: Building Europe's Cyber Shield Across Borders

 25 June 2026

 Brussels

Join us in Brussels for the COcyber Final Conference, a key gathering for cybersecurity, policy, research, industry and defence stakeholders working to strengthen Europe's response to today's complex cyber threats.

The event will explore how stronger cooperation across borders, sectors and communities can support a more resilient European cybersecurity ecosystem, with discussions on:

- ✓ dual-use innovation
- ✓ protection of democratic processes
- ✓ operational coordination
- ✓ the future of civilian-defence cooperation.

The banner features a green and yellow color scheme with a network background. On the left, a yellow bar contains the date '25 JUNE 2026'. Below it, a small icon and text specify the time '9:00 am - 17:00 pm CET' and location 'Residence Palace Brussels'. A QR code is positioned below the time. At the bottom left, logos for 'ECCC' (European Cybersecurity Competence Centre) and 'Funded by the European Union' are displayed. The main text in the center reads 'A Unified Response to Multiple Threats: Building Europe's Cyber Shield Across Borders' followed by 'FINAL CONFERENCE'. The 'cocyber' logo is in the top right, and a yellow button with the text 'Don't miss it' is in the bottom right.

[Register now](#)

A warm farewell

As COcyber comes to a close, we want to **take a moment to thank you**. Your engagement, expertise and support have helped shape this community from the start.

This may be the final edition, but the conversations, connections and ideas built through COcyber will continue beyond the project. We hope the tools, insights and collaborations shared along the way continue **to support your work towards a stronger and more connected European cybersecurity ecosystem**

Thank you for being part of this journey.

The COcyber team

This email has been sent to {{contact.EMAIL}}

You received this message because you are part of the COcyber Community.
We share updates on events, opportunities, and activities related to AI, cybersecurity, and European digital innovation

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